

DETERMINANTS OF NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY TEACHERS' PARTICIPATION IN PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES TOWARDS HEALTH PROMOTION

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to ascertain the determinant factors that influence university lecturers' participation in physical activity for the purpose of health promotion.

Methods & Materials: The participants consisted of 400 full time University lecturers. The instrument was questionnaire validated by measurement experts– Reliability co-efficient of the instrument was 0.79. ANOVA, t-test and Pearson's correlation were used for analyses.

Results: Marital status, academic qualification, work load accessibility to recreational facility and holding a position of responsibility are significant determinants of academic staff's participation in physical activity. Gender, age, staff rank and existence of official policy are not significant determinants in staff participation in PA.

Conclusion and Applications: Recreational facilities should be made available in campuses and multiple interventions should be used to enhance participation in physical activity to promote health.

KEYWORDS: Determinants, Academic Staff, Physical Activity, Participation.

INTRODUCTION

A number of experts in physical activity (PA) have consistently indicated that participation in physical activity on regular basis is an important factor in maintaining good health globally. (Ntui, 2000; Ajala 2005). Physical Activity (PA), in its broadest sense is physical exertion in which participants benefit health-wise. The physical activity includes gardening, house cleaning, washing of car, playing of balls, walking, jogging, cycling, raking of grasses/leaves, swimming, running, amongst others. Sedentary or in-active life is a slow poison to the skeletal, cardiac and visceral muscles which thrive in activity in general (Ntui 2000).

According to Berman & Snyder (2012), physical activity has some purposes: to restore, maintain or increase the tone and strength of the muscles, to maintain or increase the flexibility of joints; to maintain or promote the growth of bones through the application of physical stressors; and improve the functioning of body systems. Physical exercise has been widely reported as a sure route to physical fitness and a significant contributor to good health status. (O'Brien, 2005; Mayo Clinic Staff, 2004; Adeogun & Dansu, 2006; Bulugbe & Oloyede, 2007; Akeredolu & Adefuye, 2008).

Regular exercises could promote health by reducing the risk of death through reduction in occurrence of heart diseases, reduction of blood pressure, blood cholesterol, risk of colon and breast cancers, as well as reduction in the risk of developing diabetes. Exercise in several ways contribute to human happiness, posture, mood, decreased anxiety, depression and elevated level of self esteem among others (Centre for Disease Control, 1999; Ntui, 2000; Nutristrategy, 2004; Berman & Snyder, 2012; Doyle, 2005; Ajala, 2005; Adeogun & Dansu, 2006). Affirmatively, Karmisholt & Gotzesche (2005) reported that individuals who remain physically active or physically fit during middle and older ages live longer than their sedentary counterparts and also recommend exercise for secondary prevention of other diseases. Therefore, given the various health benefits of PA, the hazards of being inactive are clear. Physical activity in this study implies structured form of activity carried out

when one is at work and at home aimed at improving the condition and quality of heart, lungs and muscles and facilitating other physical, psychological and physiological functions of the body.

Okeneye (2002) noted that physical activity behaviour of people has been tremendously altered due to modernization or development in the society. This can be traced to advances made in technology which in some instances had led to sloth behaviour. Despite the overwhelming evidence of the positive effects of exercise, CDC (1999) had reported that more than 60 percent of the adults did not exercise regularly and 25 percent of them were not active at all. Corroborating this O'Brien (2005) still discovered that some adults are afraid that physical exercise would be too strenuous, or that it could be harmful to them. Therefore, inactivity in the populace may be related to certain determinants.

Determinants are those factors that can facilitate or hinder behavior such as participating in health promoting activity. Physical activities among university teachers is influenced by some factors such as gender, age, marital status, educational qualifications, rank, accessibility to recreational facilities, official policy making it mandatory to participate in physical activity and work load (Booth, Bauman, Owen, & Gore, 1997; Marcus, 1995). Age has been identified as one of the determinants in participation in health promoting behaviour by Health Promotion Model (HPM) (Pender, Murdaugh, & Parsons, 2002). Health Belief Model (HBM) (Rosenstock, 1974)). O'Brien (2005) also noted that inactivity increases with age and it is more common among women than men. The findings of a systematic review of participation in a worksite health promotion programme revealed contradictory results as regards age statistically highlighting significant higher and lower levels of participation among older employee (Roebroek, Lenthe, Empelen, & Burdorf, 2009). These findings are also supported by the Koeneman, Verheijden, Chinapaw, & Hopman-Rock, (2011) review on determinants of participation in physical activity and exercise.

Another demographic determinant of participating in health promotion activity is marital status as identified by Health Belief Model (HBM) (Rosenstock, 1974) and Health Promotion Model (HPM) (Pender et al, 2002). Marital status may provide the necessary social support needed for participation in health promoting behavior such as physical activity. Gender is an important variable the can determine participation in health promoting behavior. Gender is said to be one of the factors commonly examined. It has been reported that women tended to have less amounts of physical activity than their male counterparts (United State Department of Health and Human Services (USDHHS; 1996) Some physical activity programmes need to be gender sensitive in order to motivate those who are gender sensitive to participate. Marital status and gender are also identified by Health Belief Model (HBM) (Rosenstock, 1974).

There is documented evidence that despite the availability of resources for physical activity (PA) in most universities, academic staff participation in physical activity is low (Omolawon & Mohammed, 2006; Etuk, 2007). In a study conducted by Omolawon and Mohammed (2006) on perceived determinants associated with non-participation of University of Ibadan Academic Staff in sports and physical activity, the result showed that occupational demand was a determinant factor. This was represented by 51% of the respondents who agreed that occupational demands influence their participation in physical activity. The same research study showed that 49.2% of the respondents agreed that availability of sports facilities and equipment was a determinant factor in PA involvement. Affirmatively Onohwakpor and Eboh (2006) indicated facility and equipment as determinants of sport participation among College of Education, Warri, Delta State, Nigeria academic staff. Similar findings were also reported by Akeredolu & Adefuye (2008) in a study of determinants of physical activity participation in optimizing wellness among adults in rural areas of Lagos State, Nigeria. The results showed that attitude; availability of facility and equipment as well as socio-cultural variables were determinants of participation in physical activity among the population that was studied. They authors also posit that a functional facility will definitely attract the interest of people in physical activity. Shortages of facilities create problems in participating in physical activity that one chooses and there is need to provide different facilities and equipments in order to meet individual choice of activity. According to Keating, et al (2007), limited PA recreational facilities on campus may be a big problem for PA classes for academic staff and may not be a solution for increasing PA behaviours without good planning for availability and utilization of facilities.

On time or work load as determinant of participation in Physical Activity, Onohwakpor and Eboh (2006) conducted a study on perceived barriers to recreational activities for healthy living among academic staff of College of Education, Warri, Delta State, Nigeria, using 172 academic staff, the result showed that 45.9% of the respondents indicated time as barrier to recreational exercises for health promotion and maintenance. The time

stated here for university lecturers to participate in physical activity is officially made available by the university authority or management. Official policy on time, physical activity programmes, enforcement, regulation are all important determinant identified as policy factors in Ecologic Model (McLeroy, Bibeau, Steckler, & Glanz, 1988). Escoffery, Kegler, Alcantara, Wilson, M, & Glanz (2011) reported that barriers such as heavy workload and lack of time were identified in a qualitative examination of the small , rural worksites in obesity prevention in Georgia. However, Keating et al (2007) noted that University authority timing of the PA is one of the important factors in participation. Social class is also identified as a determinant in participation in sport and physical activity (Wilson, 2002). Therefore, higher academic qualification and rank which associated with higher social class may motivate people to participate in sport as recreation and physical activity to promote health.

According to Onohwakpor and Eboh (2006) despite established evidence of health related values resulting from recreational exercises, majority of Nigerians have not realized the need to participate in recreational exercises for health promotion and maintenance. The university is recognized as a centre of excellence and with the “settings approach” posited by the WHO the university is one of the settings for workplace health promotion. Secondly, academic staffs are supposed to act like models for other staff and students. There is supposed to be a high level of consciousness about health and health promotion activities but observation reveals that there is a high level of apathy which may be related to certain determinants. It therefore becomes necessary to ascertain the determinants of participation in PA in the setting of the study which is universities in Cross River State. The results of this study will help academic staff and university management to know the individual, institutional and policy variables that influence participation in physical activity and develop a comprehensive intervention to increase participation in physical activity. The main aim of the study was to ascertain the determinants of participation in physical activity with regards to gender, age, marital status, academic qualification, rank, and accessibility to recreational facilities, availability of official policy, work load and position.

The hypotheses formulated to guide the study were:

- There is no significant difference between female and male university academic staff participation in physical activity in Cross River State.
- Age will not significantly influence participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Marital status will not significantly determine participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Academic qualifications will not significantly determine participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Rank will not significantly influence participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Accessibility to recreational facilities will not significantly determine participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Availability of official policy will not significantly influence participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Work load will not significantly determine participation in physical activity among university academic staff in Cross River State.
- Position of responsibility is not a significant determinant of academic staff participation in physical activity for quality living.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The setting of the study was Cross River State of Nigeria. Cross River State is one of the thirty six (36) states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and it has eighteen (18) Local Government Areas (LGAs). The two universities in Cross River State were the sites of the study (University of Calabar and Cross River State University of Technology (CRUTECH), Calabar Campus).

At the time of the study, University of Calabar had 10 Faculties; 61 Departments, and 812 lecturers while CRUTECH had 7 Faculties; 23 Departments and 267 Lecturers which consisted of both males and females who participated in the study. Out of 17 Faculties 15 were selected for the study. Faculty of Education and College of Medical sciences were not included because of their high knowledge of the benefits of participating in physical activity. Fifty one departments out of 82 from the two universities were randomly selected. A proportionate sample of 60% from each university was used. Four hundred forty four out of 733 respondents were selected

using random sampling. The lecturers were full-time employees of the two Universities situated in Calabar, Cross River State.

The participants' ages ranged between 30 to 60 years. The participants consisted of 276 females and 124 males. With regards to marital status, 40 respondents were single while 360 were married. Two hundred and seven held positions of responsibility such as Deputy Vice Chancellor, Dean, Head of Department, Chairman of Departmental or Faculty Committee, Examination Officer, Registration Officer, Coordinator of professional examinations, Director of institute. The workload per week was graded as follows: 1-5 hours; 6-10 hours; 11-15 hours; 16-20 hours; 21-25 hours; and 25⁺ hours of teaching and research. Other characteristics of the participants include academic qualification of which majority of the respondents were Masters' degree holders (182) closely followed by Ph.D degree holders (179) below (190) followed by Lecturer II and Senior Lecturer 159 while only 51 were Associate Professors and Professors.

A self reported structured questionnaire was used in collecting the data for the study. The questionnaire was made up of 2 sections: Section A which consisted of socio-demographic information on possible determinants of involvement in physical activity for health promotion. Section B of the questionnaire focused on the participation in physical activity. A Likert scale with graded responses of Very often (VO) Often (O) Rarely (R) and Never (N) was used for section B.

The reliability of the instrument was determined using a test-retest reliability method. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used to establish the relationship. The results obtained were collated and analyzed with reliability value of 0.70. The research instrument was administered to the respondents personally by the researchers and trained field assistants. Four hundred copies of completed questionnaire were usable after collection. Prior to the administration of the instrument, an informed consent was obtained from the participants; the purpose of the study was explained to the respondents. Participants were ensured anonymity and confidentiality of the information which was to be used for research purposes. Permission to carry out the research was also obtained from the Ethical Committee of the two universities. Ninety one percent (91%) return rate was obtained.

Independent t-test; One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA); and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation were used for data analysis. Independent t-test was used for factors that have two classifications; One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for factors that have more than two classifications, while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was used for one factor (age) that was measured continuously

RESULTS

TABLE 1: Percentage analysis of academic staffs' involvement in Physical Activities for quality living

S/N	ITEMS	Often		Rarely	
		F	%	F	%
1	Walking briskly at least 2.8km in 35 minutes per day within the campus	183	46	217	54
2	Jogging at least 3 times per week	98	25	302	75
3	Bicycling for 30 minutes, 3 times a week	65	16	335	84
4	Swimming at least for 20 minutes 3 times per week	40	10	360	90
5	Running 2.5 km in 15 minutes 3 times a week	99	25	301	75
6	Playing tennis 3 times a week	66	17	334	83
7	Weight lifting for 45 minutes 3 times every week	53	13	347	87
8	Washing my floor for at least 40-60 minutes, 3 times per week	197	49	203	51
9	Playing football for at least 40 minutes at least 3 times a week	83	21	317	79
10	Dancing for at least 30 minutes 3 times per week	236	59	164	41
11	Washing of car 30 minutes 3 times a week	224	56	176	44
12	Raking grasses/leaves for 30 minutes 3 times per week	117	29	283	71
13	Washing windows and floor of my house 45 – 60 minutes 3 times per week.	176	44	224	56

Table 2 Independent t-test analysis of the influence of gender, marital status, accessibility to recreational facilities, existence of official policy and position of responsibility on academic staff's participation in physical activities.

*Significant at 0.05 level; critical t = 1.96; df = 398

Determinants (Factors)	Grouping	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Gender	Males	276	27.45	7.14	1.93
	Females	124	26.01	6.39	
Marital Status	Single	40	28.95	2.71	2.01*
	Married	360	26.64	7.21	
Accessibility to recreational facility	Yes	176	29.36	7.29	6.29*
	No	224	25.16	6.06	
Existence of official policy on physical activity	Yes	130	26.08	6.06	-1.78
	No	270	27.39	7.12	
Holding a position of responsibility	Yes	207	26.54	7.32	-2.008*
	No	193	27.94	6.39	

The results in Table 1 revealed that all items except items 10 (59%) and 11 (50%) indicated a very low involvement of academic staff in physical activities for quality living.

As observed in Table 2, the results of the data analysis show that marital status (t = 2.01); Accessibility to recreational facility (t = 6.29) and holding a position of responsibility (t = 2.00) are significant determinants of academic staff's participation in physical activity towards health promotion while gender (t = 1.93) and existence of official policy on physical activity (t = -1.78) are not significant determinants.

The results in Table 3 show that academic qualification (F = 13.65) and staff work load (F = 14.12) are significant determinants of academic staff's participation in physical activity towards health promotion, while staff rank is not a significant determinant.

The result of the analysis in Table 4 shows that there is no significant relationship between academic staff's age and their participation in physical activity towards health promotion.

Table 3: Analysis of variance of influence of academic qualification, rank and work load on academic staff's participation in physical activity.

Determinants (Factors)	Grouping	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Highest Academic Qualification	Bachelor's Degree	39	23.08	5.35	
	Masters Degree	182	28.68	6.01	
	PhD Degree	179	26.16	7.63	
	Total	400	27.01	6.94	
Rank	Lect. II & below	190	27.69	6.49	
	Lect. I & Snr. Lect.	159	26.55	7.86	
	Assoc. Prof. & Prof.	51	25.84	5.09	
	Total	400	27.01	6.94	
Work load per week (hours of teach/research)	1 – 10 hours	152	25.77	6.56	
	11 – 20 hours	181	28.92	7.54	
	Above 20 hours	67	24.63	4.27	
	Total	400	27.01	6.94	
Determinant (factor)	Source of variation	Sum of Square	df	Mean square	F-value
Highest academic qualification	Between groups	1237.05	2	618.52	13.65*
	Within groups	17984.94	397	45.30	
	Total	19221.99	399		
Rank	Between groups	191.66	2	95.83	2.00
	Within groups	19030.33	397	47.93	
	Total	19221.99	399		
Work load	Between groups	11276.46	2	47.93	14.12*
	Within groups	17945.53	397	638.23	
	Total	19221.99	399		

*Significant at 0.05 level; critical F = 3.02; df = 2 & 397

Table 4 Correlation analysis of the relationship between academic staff's age and their participation physical in activity

(N = 400)

Variable	Mean	SD	Pearson's r
Age (in years)	45.28	6.94	.055 ^{ns}
Participation in Physical Activity	27.01	6.94	

^{ns} calculated correlation is not sig. at .05 level; critical r = 165; df = 398

DISCUSSION

Generally, the results revealed low participation in physical activity by academic teachers despite knowledge of the benefits and availability of facility in the campus. The findings from this study are not surprising because apathy in participation in physical activity among university staff had been identified in previous studies by Omolawon & Mohammed, (2006) and Etuk, (2007).

Gender and participation in physical activity

The findings in this study revealed that gender did not significantly determine participation in physical activity. The result is not supported by previous findings that women tended to have less amounts of physical activity than their male counterparts (United State Department of Health and Human Services (USDHHS; 1998). Booth et al. (1997) and Marcus (1995) had reported that physical activity among university teachers was influenced by some factors such as gender, age marital status among others. Promotion Model (HPM) (Pender et al, 2002) and Health Belief Model (HBM) (Rosenstock, 1974) equally identified gender as one of the determinants in participating in health promoting behavior. Gender is an important variable that can determine participation in health promoting behavior. Some physical activity programmes need to be gender sensitive in order to motivate both sexes to participate.

Age and participation in physical activity

With regards to age not being a significant determinant of participation in physical activity in this study, it was also identified as one of the determinants in participating in health promoting behaviour by Health Promotion Model (HPM) (Pender et al, 2002) and Health Belief Model (HBM) (Rosenstock, 1974) The findings in this study is supported by the results of a systematic review of participation in worksite health promotion programme which revealed contradictory results for age with both statistically significant higher and lower levels of participation among older employee (Robroek et al. 2009). The contradictory results were also supported by Koenema (2011) review on determinants of physical activity and exercise.

Marital status and participation in physical activity

The results revealed that marital status was a significant determinant of participating in physical activity among university academic staff. The finding is supported by Health Belief Model (HBM) (Rosenstock, 1974) Health Promotion Model Pender et al. (HPM) and (Pender et al, 2002) which identified marital status as one of the determinants in participating in health promoting activity. Marital status may provide the necessary social support needed for participation in health promoting behavior such as physical activity.

Academic qualification and participation in physical activity

The findings that academic qualification is a significant determinant in participating in physical activity among university academic staff is supported by the assertion that social class is a determinant in participation in sport and physical activity (Wilson, 2002). Therefore, higher academic qualification and rank which is associated with higher social class may be motivation to participate in sport as recreation and physical activity to promote health.

Rank and participation in physical activity

In this study it was discovered that rank was not a significant determinant in participating in physical activity among university academic staff. This result is may be related to university policy of employing those with PhD as Lecturer II which does not show that those with terminal degree will be given higher rank. Irrespective of the rank in the workplace the benefits of participating in physical activity should encourage people to engage in physical activity.

Accessibility to recreational facility and participation in physical activity

The findings of the study revealed that accessibility to recreational facilities were significant determinants of academic staff participation in physical activity. the result agree with studies conducted by Omolawon and Mohammed (2006); Onohwakpor and Eboh (2006); Akeredolu & Adefuye (2008) on perceived determinants associated with non-participation in sports and physical activity. Omolawon and Mohammed (2006) reported on determinants of participation of academic staff of University of Ibadan in physical activity, the research study showed that 49.2% of the respondents agreed that availability of sports facilities and equipment was a determinant factor in PA involvement. Affirmatively Onohwakpor and Eboh (2006) reported facility and equipment as determinants of sport participation among College of Education academic staff. Similar findings were also reported by Akeredolu & Adefuye (2008).

Official policy and participation in physical activity

Official policy was not a significant determinant of academic staff's participation in physical activity in this study. This result is in contrast with WHO notion on workplace as a setting for health promotion which emphasizes official policy to encourage workers to participate in health promoting behavior since they spend 60 per cent of their 24 hours at work (2008). The workplace also offers an efficient structure to reach large group, and makes use of a natural social network (Robroek et al., 2009, WHO 2008) therefore, official policy is an imperative to encourage participation in exercise is imperative. Time allocation for physical exercise, types of exercise programmes, incentives will all be specified in the policy.

Staffs work load and participation in physical activity

Work load and lack of time were determinant factors in academic staff's participation in physical activity as evidenced in this study. The result is supported by Onohwakpor and Eboh (2006); Omolawon and Mohammed (2006) studies on barriers to recreational activities for healthy living among academic staff of College of Education, Warri Delta State, Nigeria and University of Ibadan, Nigeria respectively, which revealed that time was a barrier to participation in recreational sport and physical activity to promote health. The allotted time here is officially made available by the university authority and it exists as a policy in the institution. However, Keating et al (2007) noted that University authority timing of the PA is one of the important factors in participation.

Position of responsibility and participation in physical activity

The findings of the study showed that position of responsibility was a significant determinant in academic staff's participation in physical activity. The result may be related to the fact that a position of responsibility in the university goes with additional workload to teaching and research supervision. Additionally, such an academic staff is expected to publish academic/research papers or lose promotion. These activities imply a tight schedule which may not favour participation in any recreational activity including physical activity. Therefore, academic staffs irrespective of geographical location seem to have same characteristic that influence their participation in physical activity.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions made from the result of the research were that marital status, academic qualification, accessibility to recreational facility and holding a position of responsibility are significant determinants of academic staffs participation in physical activity towards health promotion, gender, age, staff rank and existence of official policy are not significant determinants of academic staff's participation in physical activity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the research results it is recommended that lecturers should be motivated to use the recreational facilities available on Universities campuses rather than just policy formulation which often end up being an official document. Also regular seminars should be organized to sensitize the vulnerable group of academic staff of the dangers of not taking/doing exercise to promote health. Workload as a result of holding position of responsibility for academic staff should be addressed so as to encourage participation in recreational physical activity. Interventions to increase physical activity should be gender and age sensitive

REFERENCES

- Adeogun, F. & Dansu, T. (2006). Exercise and fitness behaviour of market men and women in Badagry LGA Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of International Council for Health, Physical Education, Recreation, Sport and Dance* 1(2), 55 - 58.
- Ajala, J. (2005). *Health education in wellness and sickness: This day, this age*. An Inaugural lecture delivered at the University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria.
- Akeredolu, O. A. & Adefuye, M. A. (2008). Determinants of physical activity participation in optimizing wellness among adults in rural areas of Lagos State, Nigeria. 4th International Council for Health, Physical Education, Recreation, sport and Dance (ICHPER-SD) African Regional Congress 14th -17th October 2008
- Berman A, Snyder S (2012). *Kozier & Erb's Fundamentals of Nursing: Concepts, Process and Practice*. (9TH ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.

Booth, M. L., Bauman, A., Owen, N. & Gore, C. (1997). Physical activity preferences, preferred sources of assistance and perceived barriers to increased activity among physically inactive Australian. *Preventive Medicine*, 26: 131 - 137

Bulugbe, T. A., & Oloyede, T. A. (2007). The place of physical activities and wellness in achieving Millennium Development Goals. *Journal of International Council for Health, Physical Education, recreation, Sport and Dance*, 1(2), 21-24.

Centre for Disease Control (1999). A new view of physical activity at a glance Available: <http://www.cdc.gov/nccd/php/sgr/ataglan.htm> (15th Feb. 2005).

Doyle, J. A. (2005) The benefits of exercise (online) Available: http://www.2.gsu.edu/www_fit/benefits.Html. (15th Feb 2005)

Escoffery, C., Kegler, M. C., Alcantara, I., Wilson, M., & Glanz, K. A. (2011). A qualitative examination of the role of small, rural worksites in obesity prevention. *Prev Chronic Dis* 8(4): A75 Available:http://www.cdc.gov/pcd/issues/2011/jul/10_0185.htm (May 20, 2012).

Keating, X. D., Haung, Y. Haung, J., Chen, L., Pinero, J. C., Bridges D., & Deng, M. (2007). Promoting University personnel's physical activity behaviours: A review and synthesis. *The ICHPERSD Journal of Research in Health, Physical Education, Recreation, Sport & Dance*, 11(1), 1 – 5

Karmisholt, K. & Gotzesche, P. C. (2005). Physical activity for secondary prevention of diseases. Systemic review of randomized clinical trials. *Dan Med Bull*, 52 (2), 90 - 94

Koeneman. M. A., Verheijden, M. W., Chinapaw, M. J. M., & Hopman-Rock, M. (2011). Determinants of physical activity and exercise in healthy older adults: A systematic review. *International Journal of Behavioural Nutrition and Physical Activity* 8: 142 Available from:<http://www.ijbnpa.org/content/8/1/142> (May 20, 2012)

Mayo Clinic Staff (2004). "your fitness program tips for staying motivated. Available <http://www.mayoclinic.com/invite.cfm?Id=HQ01443> (15th February, 2005.)

McLeroy, K., Bibeau, D. Steckler, A., & Glanz, K. (1988). An ecological perspective on health promotion programmes. *Health Educ Q*, 15 (4), 351 - 377.

Marcus, B. H. (1995). Exercise behaviour and strategies for intervention. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sports*. 66: 319 - 325.

Ntui, E. P. (2000). *Aerobics and prolonged intensive studies for secondary and tertiary institutions*. Calabar: University of Calabar Press.

Nutristrategy. (2004). "Health benefits of exercises (online) Available: <http://www.Nutristrategy.com/health.Htm> (15th Feb. 2005).

O'Brien, S. (2005). The benefits of exercise for seniors: it is never too late to improve your health. Available: <http://seniorliving.About.com/b/a/137067.htm> (Feb 15, 2005)

Okeneye, R. E. (2002). Regular exercise and individual's health. *Nigerian Journal of Physical, Health Education and Recreation (NIJHER)*, 2: 5 -10.

Omolawon, K. O., & Mohammed S. (2006). Perceived determinants associated with non-participation of University of Ibadan academic staff in sport and physical activities. *Journal of International Council for Health, Physical Education, Recreation, sport and Dance*, 1(2), 97-100.

Onohwapor, A.E. O., & Eboh, L.O. (2006). Percieved barriers to recreational activities for healthy living among academic staff of College of Education, Warri, Delta State. *Journal of International Council for Health, Physical Education, recreation, Sport and Dance*, 1(2), 109-133.

Pender, N. J., Murdaugh, C.L., & Parsons M. A. (2002). Health Promotion Model (Revised). (4th ed.). Prentice Hall: New Jersey.

Roebroek, S. J. W., Lenthe, F. J. V., Empelen, P.V., & Burdorf, A. (2009). Determinants of participation in worksites health promotion programmes: a systematic review. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity* 6: 26 Available from:<http://www.ijbnpa.org/content/6/1/26> (May 20, 2012)

Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). Historical origin of the Health Belief Model. In Becker MH eds. The Health Belief Model and personal health behavior. Thorofare NJ: Charles B. Slack.

United State Department of Health and Human Services. (USDHHS) (1996). Physical activity and health. A report of Surgeon general. Atlanta, G. A: US Department of Health and Human Services, Centre for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion.

Wilson, T. C. (2002). Towards improving Nigeria performance in international sports competitions. *Journal of the National Institute for Sports*, 1(1), 1- 8

WHO (2008). The workplace as a setting for interventions to improve diet and promote physical activity . WHO Press. Geneva, Switzerland. Available [http:// www. Who.int./dietphysicalactivity/Quintiliani-work-place-as-setting.pdf](http://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/Quintiliani-work-place-as-setting.pdf) (2nd September, 2011)

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